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Quinoline-Based Polyazaheterocycles by a Hydrogen Peroxide-Mediated Isocyanide Insertion

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Abstract

An efficient and green protocol for the synthesis of quinoline-based polyazaheterocycles with 2-(2-mercaptoquinolin-3-yl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones and aliphatic and aromatic isocyanides using hydrogen peroxide is described.

Keywords: Hydrogen peroxide; insertion; isocyanide; polyazaheterocycles; quinolones; thiazines.